

The Knowledge of Families for Dengue Haemorrhagic Fever Prevention at Fatuqueiro Village in Ermera Municipality of Timor Leste

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ABSTRACT

Dengue is a health problem for the population of Timor-Leste and has often occurred and has been destroyed by many people, and dengue in the past is an pandemic of severe dengue disease, but at the moment dengue disease has been a severe disease influenced by environmental factors such as the disposal of waste, poor water sanitation, which has caused a great risk of the occurrence of dengue disease, The Ministry of Health Timor Reported from January to October 2022 with a total of 2.374 cases of dengue with a total of 31 cases fatality rate is 1,3%, the majority of cases detected in Dili Municipality with 1.488 total cases and Ermera municipality is about 90 cases, following by Baucau municipality with 25 cases. Objective of the research is to identify the knowledge of families with dengue prevention at Fatuqueiro Village. Total 85 families at Fatuqueiro village in Ermera Municipality, it's showed only 76,5% of families understand the dengue hemorrhagic fever (DHF) prevention and the rest of families don't understand how to prevent dengue hemorrhagic fever. Also analysis of the Correlation Statistics test showed P-value of $0,000 < 0,5$ means that there is a significant relationship knowledge with DHF prevention and r value is 0,946 which is located between 0,0,0-1,00 has showed perfect relationship. The knowledge of families understand how o prevent from DHF is 75,5% and perfect relationship between knowledge of families with DHF prevention by families at Fatuqueiro village in Ermera Municipality, Timor Leste. The knowledge of families perfect correlation with DHF prevention in Fatuqueiro village

INTRODUCTION

Dengue is a health problem for the population of Timor-Leste and has often occurred and has been destroyed by many people, and dengue in the past is an pandemic of severe dengue disease, but at the moment dengue disease has been a severe disease influenced by environmental factors such as the disposal of waste, poor water sanitation, which has caused a great risk of the occurrence of dengue disease, and has caused the death of many people, and it is seen that every year cases of dengue disease have always increased the number of cases affected and the number of deaths, as a result of minimal treatment, which also affects the lives of people. The World Health Organization (2022), which was published by the Pan American Health Organization (PAHO) an increase in the number of cases of dengue fever (DHF) and a confirmed case of dengue a total 1.8 per billion born in the Asia Pacific Region with a ratio and approach of 90% and out of 75% affected dengue Shock Syndrome (DSS) and a cumulative 2.5% for children who die from dengue fever, even though they are treated in hospitals. And Also the eepidemiology surgey report (2022), the total number of cases from January to October 2022 with a total of 2.374 cases of dengue with a total of 31 CFR 1,3%, the majority of cases detected by the Municipality of Dili with a total of 1488 case, Emera 90 case, Bacau 25 case, Manatt 23 case and Cova lima 17 case, Manufahi 14 case, Boxboard 5 case, Acinar 4 case, Iquique 4 case , Laquita 3 case, Ailed 1 case, Oecussi 3 case, almost 3 cases of dengue affected the population throughout the territory of Timor Lester. And cases of dengue in all Municipalities were based on the 2022 age group, and the most widely affected age range < 14 years as well as the age group of 5-14 years with a total of 41,8% and the age group of 1-4 with a total of 36,5%.

The result survei by Tilman et al. (2020) shows that dengue fever with a total of 1.451 cases of mobility and mortality with 10 cases of fatality rate of 0,7% and in the capital of Dili was the majority of cases with a total of 815 cases and 7 cases of death, and in 2021 a total of 901 cases of dengue fever had been killed by 11 people with 1.2% and the Municipality of Dili with a total of 672 cases and 8 deaths.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Timor-Leste is a country with sufficient cold temperatures in the tropic zone so that it is easy to provide space for *Aedes Aegypti* mosquito to develop itself and the mosquito itself is a vector of dengue, as long as the dengue virus is easily injected through *aedes aegypti* mosquito, which is a cause factor that affects health problems with transmission which has started to be deep so that it causes an increase in the number of diseases and deaths among the community, (WHO, 2016). To overcome these problems and cases it is necessary to prevent dengue fever and increase the knowledge of head of family to evaluate and control public health and sanitation problems for families, in relation to the occurrence of dengue fever, as well as increase and increase the knowledge of families about the level of prevention that is the foundation of dengue fever that greatly affects babies and adults with current situations in Timor-Leste and the Future, (WHO, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is a way that is carried out in the research process to obtain data for the purposes and uses contained in it (Hidayat, 2017).

The method of research used quantitative method in relation to cross-sectional time approach. Quantitative methods are techniques used to process data in the form of numbers and by use statistics, as a result of the tools available, (Norodom, 2012). The location of the research at Fatuquero Village, Administrative Post of Railaco, Municipality of Ermera.

The objects of the population taken by the research were the the Families stay at Fatuquero Village in Ermera Municipality. of Timor Leste

The sample size was taken by the researcher was 85 samples. The sampling technique is used probability sampling method, with the type of Cluster sampling. The instrument of research used is a questionnaire to collect data and value its findings. Analysis of statistical data type frequency distributions and the product moment correlation to understand correlation of indepent and depedent variable.

RESULTS

The Characteristics of Families

The families to participated in this study are 85 families with mayority between aged 37-53 years old is 42,4% and 24-36 years and 54-72 years old with each 22,4% and 35,3%. If look at part of gender perspective, there are 78,8% of male and 21,8% of males. And also this study need understand the level of education the families distributed in Fatuquero village are mayority with secondary level of education is 34,1% and illiterate of 23,5%.

Access to Health Information

To improving the knowledge of families distributed at Fatuquero village is as below

Table 1. The Distribution Frequency Source of Health Information to Access by Families in Fatuquero Village

No	Sources	n	%
1	Radio / television	32	37.6
2	Internet	4	4.7
3	Health Personal	49	57.6
Total		85	100

The majority of the Family in Fatuquero village have access to information sources from Health Professionals with 49 families (57.6%), while the minority has access to information sources from the Internet with 4 families (4.7%).

The Knowledge Families

Table 2. The Knowledge of Family is Very Important on Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever Prevention

No	Level of education	n	%
1	Good	7	8.2
2	Sufficinet	13	15.3
3	Low	65	76.5
Totak		85	100

The majority of Family in Fatuquero village had a lack of knowledge about dengue fever because of 76.5% from families low undestanding on prevention DHF.

The Correlation Knowledge of Families With DHF Prevention

The understand of correlation knowledge of families on DHF prevention need to analyse correlation test results with prevention DHF in Fatuquero village to done product moment correlation analysis showed the correlation Statistics test, which has a significant value of p value of 0,000 below the value of < 0,5 means that there is a significant relationship between knowledge and the way of prevention and the results of correlation with the value of $r = 0,946$ which is located between 0,0,0-1,00 categories of stronger correlation with perfect correlation.

DISCUSSION

Based on the research process conducted on the knowledge of the Head of the Family regarding the way of prevention dengue disease in Fatuquero Village in Ermera Municipality of Timor Leste with 85 families showed majority of the Family with aged 37-53 is 42.4%. Report from Health Department Republic Indonesia (2019), the age as an arrangement of time for measuring objects of life and death is measured from birth and has started to be counted according to the change in time. The level of education is a part of manner to DHF prevention but result this study show the level of education is mayority (34,1%) on secondary school level and also understanding families to prevent DHF also very low (76,5%).Mayority families access health information from health professional (57.6%), and the minority has access to information sources from the Internet about 4.7%., The knowledge is a determining factor in the modification and development of the individual's opinion, the attitude of forming a person's behavior is more mature to be able to apply for all activities, (Notoatmodjo, 2015). The results of the analysis of Correlation Statistics test with a significant value P of 0,000 shows that the value of 0,000 is lower than the value of 0,5 means that there is a significant relationship between knowledge and the way of prevention dengue disease and the correlation value of $r = 0,946$ which is located between 0,0-1,00 the category of perfect correlation. Similarly, research conducted by Yanyan Bahtiar, Herlina Susmaneli, Wahyu Mahardika, (2016) shows that there is a significant relationship between knowledge and the way in which denge disease prevention is worth $0,000 < 0,5$ and the correlation value is 0,01-0,97 which means that between the variables of knowledge and the attitude of

prevention of dengue disease have a significant relationship and a stronger correlation with the positive relationship.

Analysis of the two variables to be known in the relationship or there is no relationship between the two variables themselves, whether the statistical test with value ($P < 0,05$) is related or correlation, whether the statistical test with value ($P > 0,05$) is not related. And the coefficient correlation of the r with criteria starting from $0,199$ with a lower category, $0,20-0,399$ with a lower category, $0,40-0,599$ with a sufficient strength category, $0,60-0,799$ with a stronger category, $0,80-1,00$ with stronger categories. To find out the relationship between the variable independent and dependent and the statistical examination will be carried out using the type of Correlation Spearman Rank, (Notoatmodjo, 2014).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The result of analyses show that majority of family finish at secondary school and some of them lower than that, the profession majority are agriculture.

The knowledge of families understand how to prevent from DHF is 75,5% and perfect relationship between knowledge of families with DHF prevention by families at Fatuquero village in Ermera Municipality, Timor Leste. The knowledge of families perfect correlation with DHF prevention in Fatuquero village.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of The Knowledge of Families for dengue hemorrhagic fever prevention at Fatuqueiro Village in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

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